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Effect of Different Lighting Schedule on Growth Performance of Broiler Chicken

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Received Date: 27-Jan-2022 Accepted Date: 16-Mar-2022 Published Date: 30-Apr-2022

Abstract

This study was conducted at LSPU Compound, Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines, from September 23, 2018, to October 28, 2018. A Randomized Completely Block Design was used to determine the effect of different lighting program on growth performance of the broilers chicken from 15 to 35 days of age.

The treatments used were: T1 Control 15-21 days 6am to 5 am Light: 5am to 6am Dark. T2 15-21 days 6am-10pmLight :10 pm-6amDark 21-28 days 6am- 11pmLight:11pm- 2amDark 2am- 3amLight:3am-6amDark 28-31 days 6am-12pmLight:12pm-2amDark 2am-4am:4am-6amDark 31-35 days 6am-1amLight :1am-2amD 2am-5amLight :5am-6amDark. T3 15-35days 6am-2amLight:2am-6amDark.T4 15-21days 6am-10pmLight:10pm-6amDark 21-28 days 6am-9pmLight:9pm-2amDark 29-31days, 6am-2amLight:2am-6amDark31-35days6am-3amLight:3am-8amDark 8am1pmLight:1pm-4pmDark. Result showed that the average final body weight of the experimental broiler chickens ranges from 1560.37 to 1496.43g while the cumulative feed consumption at 35 days of age also ranges from 2085.80g to 2077.51g per bird. The lowest average feed conversion ratio observed was 1.93g with the highest at 2.09g while highest average daily gain observed at 35 days of age was 52.77g while the lowest is 48.63g. The average cost of feeds needed to produce a kilogram of body weight gain is Php89.26 for Treatment 2 and Php84.25 for Treatment 1. Analysis of variance or covariance was detected, a significant different on body weight of 35 days and among the average final performances of feed consumption. On the other hand, the different duration of red LED in the broilers has a significant effect on the body weight at 35 days old.

It can be concluded that the different lighting schedule across treatment has no effect on feed consumption and feed conversion ratio. However, the use of intermittent use of dark and light particularly T2 and T4 can boost weight gain while minimizing the cost of electricity.

Keywords: lightning schedule, growth performance, schedule, LED light

Introduction

Light is a vital environmental factor in broiler chicken production, and the lighting schedule has a positive effect as it saves more light energy.

There is a issue whether light is vital to incidences of diseases, or it attributes to fast growth. Decreased photoperiods are reported to decrease susceptibility to metabolic diseases such as ascites associated with pulmonary hypertension syndrome, sudden death syndrome, tibial dyschondroplasia, and other skeletal disorders. Additionally, intermittent lighting programs can reduce lameness and circulatory problems in broilers and roasters (Petek et al., 2005).

Red light reduces aggressiveness, as measured by the frequency of vigorous pecks and distress calls) compared to white light and hens in green light engaged more in foraging and explorative behavior (Huber-Eicher et al., 2013).

The effect of lighting on broiler is a topic that has been studied for many years. Intensity, wavelength, photoperiod, type and placement of lighting all play a vital part in bird development and performance. Since light bulbs were invented, the primary source of lighting for avian of all types has been incandescent lighting. Over the last 3 decades and increasing dramatically in recent years, different types of lighting have been introduced into houses and poultry barns as well. Modern lights are much more energy efficient and still provide adequate illumination.

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Lighting is a powerful exogenous factor in control of many physiological and behavioral processes. Light may be the most critical of all environmental factors to birds. It is integral to sight, including both visual acuity and color discrimination (Manser, 1996).

Since electricity cost nowadays is expensive, it is important to learn how lighting schedule would affect broiler chicken productivity and in relation to profitability. Thus, the aimed of this study was to determine if lighting schedule of duration (photoperiod) can affect performance in broiler chickens.

Statement of the Problem

The aimed of this study was to determine the effects of different lighting sources in growth performance of broiler chickens specifically this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the effect of different lighting schedule on the growth performance of broilers chicks in the ration in terms of: body weight, average daily gain, feed consumption, feed conversion ratio, and net income over electricity

2. Is there a significant difference on the effects of the different lighting schedule on the growth performance of broiler chickens?

3. Which lighting schedule was more economical for broilers chickens' production?

Hypothesis

This null hypothesis that the effects of the different lighting schedule on the growth performance of broilers are not significant different was tested in this study.

Conceptual framework of the study

The independent and dependent variables are presented in figure 1. independent are the difference lighting program. Employed per treatment the effect of which were measured and compared with the effect of other treatment these are presented order dependent variable as follow body weight, average daily gain, feed consumption, feed conversion ratio and net income over electricity cost.

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Figure 1. Paradigm of relationship between independent and dependent variables.

Literature Review

Chickens (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) are a gallinaceous domesticated fowl, bred and raised specifically for meat production. The total growth rate for the year 2012-13 was 7.8 per cent with highest total growth rate of 13.2 per cent was in 2011-12 due to the inclusion of production for commercial poultry (BAHS,2012).

Chicken eye is superior to the livestock eye and can discriminate light color, furthermore, it can be able to see a broader portion of the light spectrum compared to human (380 to 760 nm) (Prescott and Wathes, 1999; Er. et al., 2007). Therefore, most of the recent research have focused on restricting light regimens to improve productivity of broiler chickens because the physical activity is very low during darkness and energy expenditure of activity is considerable (Rahimi et al., 2005).

For decades, broiler chickens have usually been reared under continuous or near continuous (23L:1D) photoperiods to maximize feed consumption and growth rate. However, several investigations showed that using continuous light programs induces sleep deprivation and causes severe physiological stress responses (Campo and Davila, 2002; Kliger et al., 2000).

In poultry production practices, it has been observed that difference in light intensity can affect broiler behavior. Most common activity level has been seen to vary due to light intensity (Kristensen et al., 2006; Alvino et al., 2009). The artificial light offered to birds in commercial production systems can be altered in intensity. These artificial light sources are designed primarily for human vision, and it has even been suggested that they may not be suitable for the vision of all birds (Kliger et al. 2000) reported that using an intermittent instead of a non-intermittent restricted light program can have an immune enhancing effect on broiler chickens

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(Moore and Siopes 2000). reported improved cellular and humoral immune responses for Japanese quail raised under decreasing photoperiods compared to quail raised under continuous light condition.

They may not be suitable for the vision of all birds (Evans et al., 2012). Photoperiod regimens have been reported to affect broiler performance. Performance is generally evaluated based on differences in body weight, feed efficiency, and livability.

The effect of lighting on chickens is a topic that has been studied for many years. Intensity, wavelength, photoperiod, type, and placement of lighting all play an important part in bird development and performance. Since light bulbs were invented, the primary source of lighting for avian of all types has been incandescent lighting. Over the last 3 decades and increasing dramatically in recent years, different types of lighting have been introduced into houses and poultry barns as well. Modern lights are much more energy efficient and still provides adequate illumination. This has required new research on the entire lighting management system for growing broilers. Three of the most common replacements for the incandescent bulb are fluorescent, metal halide, and high-pressure sodium (Olanrewaju et al 2006).

Light is a central environmental factor in broiler production. Light affects growth rate, animal welfare, and production economy. There are 4 important main features of light: light intensity, photoperiod, light source, and spectrum of light (Manser, 1996).

Photoperiod an example of light duration is the second major aspect of light that will alter broiler performance. Most research involving light management has focused on this factor. Different photoperiodic regimes have been applied and tested over the years, while almost all of them have been shown to improve broiler welfare with conventional near-continuous lighting (Gordon, 1994).

Photoperiod administration have been reported to affect broiler performance. Performance is generally evaluated based on differences in body weight, feed efficiency, and livability (Beane et al. 1962).

Red light reduces aggressiveness, as measured by the frequency of vigorous pecks and distress calls) compared to white light and hens in green light engaged more in foraging and explorative behavior (Huber-Eicher et al., 2013).

General Observation

During the experimental period it was observed that there was no sign of illness and parasite infection resulting to 0% mortality. Another was low heat emitted by the LED light. During hot weather leads the chicks to consume less feeds. But after a week where the chicks were acclimatized, they tend to consume their feeds and become more active.

Body Weight

Body weight determines the readiness of broiler chicken for market. The average body weights of the broiler from the different treatments from the start up to the end of the study in a weekly interval are presented in Table 2. The chickens with different lighting schedule of LED bulbs gave the heaviest mean cumulative gain in weight of 1560.37g while the lightest bird with 1419.09g was observed from the group treated with different lighting schedule form 6:00am-5:00am-6:00pm. Analysis of variance and covariance, however, detected during 35 days of the experiment significant difference among treatment means was observed this result indicator that different lighting schedule significantly affect the average weekly body weight of broiler chickens statistical analysis showed that body weight of broiler chicken in T2 and T4 were not significant different from each other but significantly different the most of the treatment (Freeman et al., 1981).

However, this result contradicts with the study that introduction of a moderate day length of 16hours is associated with potential welfare benefits. Including lower physiological stress, improved immune response, increased sleep, increased overall activity, and improvement in bone metabolism and leg health. Performance of broiler chickens is improved by intermittent lighting of repeated cycles of 1 hour light and 2 hour darkness schedules compared to continuous lighting. (Gordon, 1994; Davis et al., 1997; Rozenboim et al.,1999b),

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Table 2. Average cumulative weekly body in weight of the experimental broilers in grams

TREATMENT	Mean cumulative gain in weight, in grams		
	21 Days	28 Days	35 Days
T1	623.75	1207.50	1419.09 ^b
T2	598.75	1158.75	1496.43 ^{ab}
T3	630.00	1196.25	1472.62 ^b
T4	659.75	1222.25	1560.37 ^a
F	3.85	1.11	6.48
P	0.056 ^{ns}	0.4006 ^{ns}	0.0157*
CV(%)	4.45	4.76	3.28

Legend:

T1 Age	Light	Dark	T4 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-5AM	5AM-6PM	15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
T2 Age	Light	Dark	22-28	6AM-9PM	9PM-2AM
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM	29-31	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
22-28	6AM-11PM	11PM-2AM	32-35	6AM-3AM	3AM-8AM
	2AM-3AM	3AM-6AM		8AM-1PM	1PM-4PM
29-31	6AM-12AM	12AM-2AM			
	2AM-4AM	4AM-6AM			
32-35	6AM-1AM	1AM-2AM			
	2AM-5AM	5AM-6AM			
T3 Age	Light	Dark			
15-35	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM			

Feed Consumption

The highest average cumulative feed consumption of 2085.80g as presented in Table 3 was observed from the broilers treated with different lighting schedule T4 while the lowest average cumulative weekly feed consumption of 2074.71g was obtain from the experimental units fed with pure commercial feeds (Table 3). Analysis of variance, however, failed to detect any significant difference on the feed consumption of the experimental animals which implies that the treated with different time duration did not significantly influence the appetite of the broilers (Yahav et al. 2000).

Table 3. Average cumulative weekly feed consumption of broiler, in grams

TREATMENT	Mean cumulative feed consumption, in grams		
	15-21Days	21-28 Days	28-35 Days
T1	379.25	1095.07	2074.71
T2	379.38	1094.67	2074.92
T3	380.60	1096.47	2077.51
T4	385.31	1103.91	2085.80
F	7.57	4.92	6.72
P	0.082 ^{ns}	0.0271 ^{ns}	0.115 ^{ns}
CV(%)	0.5440	0.3549	0.1931

Legend:

T1 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-5AM	5AM-6PM
T2 Age	Light	Dark
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-11PM	11PM-2AM
	2AM-3AM	3AM-6AM
29-31	6AM-12AM	12AM-2AM
	2AM-4AM	4AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-1AM	1AM-2AM
	2AM-5AM	5AM-6AM
T3 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM

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T4 Age	Light	Dark
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-9PM	9PM-2AM
29-31	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-3AM	3AM-8AM
	8AM-1PM	1PM-4PM

Feed Conversion Efficiency

The feed conversion efficiency determines the ability of the birds to convert the feeds they eat into body weight gain. Together with good animal health and favorable conditions, efficiency of feed conversion increases the profit at constant prices. The lower the feed conversion ratio value, the higher the profit. The average feed conversion efficiency of the broiler from the different treatments from the start up to the end of the study in a weekly interval is presented in Table 4. The chicken treated with different lighting schedule gave the highest mean final feed conversion efficiency of 2.09 while the lowest feed conversion efficiency of 1.93 was observed. Analysis of variance, however, failed to detect any significant difference on the feed conversion efficiency of the experimental animals this result implies that the bird treated with different lighting schedule did not significantly influence the appetite of the broilers (Blatchford et al. 2009).

Table 4. Average weekly feed conversion efficiency of broilers, in grams

TREATMENT	Mean feed conversion efficiency		
	15-21 Days	21-28 Days	28-35 Days
T1	1.87	1.42	2.00
T2	1.90	1.43	1.93
T3	1.91	1.42	2.03
T4	1.76	1.69	2.09
F	2.61	2.60	1.06
P	0.1464 ^{ns}	0.1477 ^{ns}	0.4353 ^{ns}
CV(%)	13.85	12.62	5.07

Legend:

T1 Age	Light	Dark	T3 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-5AM	5AM-6PM	15-35	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
T2 Age	Light	Dark			
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM			
22-28	6AM-11PM	11PM-2AM	T4- Age	Light	Dark
	2AM-3AM	3AM-6AM	15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
29-31	6AM-12AM	12AM-2AM	22-28	6AM-9PM	9PM-2AM
	2AM-4AM	4AM-6AM	29-31	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-1AM	1AM-2AM	32-35	6AM-3AM	3AM-8AM
	2AM-5AM	5AM-6AM		8AM-1PM	1PM-4PM

Average Daily Gain

The average daily gain of birds during experimental period is shown in Table 5. Experimental birds in Treatment 4 obtained the highest mean of 52.77 grams and followed by treatment 2 which obtained 51.25 grams. Treatment 1 got an average daily gain of 49.64 grams while Treatment 3 obtained the lowest mean of 11.60 grams.

In the analysis of variance revealed that there were not significant differences on the different lighting schedule on the average daily gain of the chicken used the study.

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Table 5. Average Daily Gain of broilers, in grams

TREATMENT	Mean Average Daily Gain	
	15-35 Days	
T1	49.64	
T2	51.25	
T3	48.63	
T4	52.77	
F	2.84	
P	0.1464 ^{ns}	
CV(%)	4.2785	

Legend:

<i>T1 Age</i>	<i>Light</i>	<i>Dark</i>
15-35	6AM-5AM	5AM-6PM
<i>T2 Age</i>	<i>Light</i>	<i>Dark</i>
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-11PM	11PM-2AM
	2AM-3AM	3AM-6AM
29-31	6AM-12AM	12AM-2AM
	2AM-4AM	4AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-1AM	1AM-2AM
	2AM-5AM	5AM-6AM
<i>T3 Age</i>	<i>Light</i>	<i>Dark</i>
15-35	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
<i>T4 Age</i>	<i>Light</i>	<i>Dark</i>
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-9PM	9PM-2AM
29-31	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-3AM	3AM-8AM
	8AM-1PM	1PM-4PM

Net Income Over Electricity Cost

Table 6 shows the average of Net Income over electricity cost (pesos). It shows that treatment 4 with 103.41 NIOEC beneficial followed by treatment 3 with Php76.97 and treatment 2 are Php71.86. Treatment 1 got the least NIOEC with Php65.85.

Observing electricity costs was beneficial by using Led lights lessen the electricity cost (Hesham Mohammed 2010).

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Table 6. Production Income (PhP)

TREATMENT	Mean Production Income			Mean average daily gain 15-35 Days
	Feeds (PhP)	Price of Light (PhP)	Treatment (PhP)	
T1	26	2.87	2.58	65.85
T2	26	2.00	2.84	71.86
T3	26	2.00	1.73	76.97
T4	26	2.00	1.33	103.41
F	-	-	-	2.03
P	-	-	-	0.1803 ^{ns}
CV(%)	-	-	-	13.9588

Legend:

T1 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-5AM	5AM-6PM
T2 Age	Light	Dark
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-11PM	11PM-2AM
	2AM-3AM	3AM-6AM
29-31	6AM-12AM	12AM-2AM
	2AM-4AM	4AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-1AM	1AM-2AM
	2AM-5AM	5AM-6AM
T3 Age	Light	Dark
15-35	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
T4 Age	Light	Dark
15-21	6AM-10PM	10PM-6AM
22-28	6AM-9PM	9PM-2AM
29-31	6AM-2AM	2AM-6AM
32-35	6AM-3AM	3AM-8AM
	8AM-1PM	1PM-4PM

Summary of Findings

The results of the study can be summarized as follows:

1. The average final body weight, of broiler chicken was significant by affected by the treatment employed in 28 to 35 days in the study.
2. The average total feed consumption was significantly influenced by the treatment employed.
3. The highest average feed conversion ratio was observed from treatment 4 2.09 and treatment 1 with 2.00 followed by the chickens in treatment T3 2.03 and the lowest is treatment 2 with 1.93. The average final Feed Conversion efficiency, average daily gain and net income over electricity cost of the broiler chickens were not significantly affected by the treatment applied.

Conclusions

Based in the findings it was concluded that the average weekly final body weight and total feed consumption were affected by the effects of different lighting schedule on the growth performance of broiler chicken. However, feed consumption efficiency, average daily gain and production were not affected by the treatments.

Recommendations

1. For a heavier body weight at 35 days of age broilers should the use of recommend on the following lighting schedule at 15-21days with 6am-10pm Light:10pm-6am Dark 21-28 days 6am-9pm Light:9pm-2am Dark 28-31days 6am-2am Light:2am-6am Dark 31-35 days 6am-3am Light :3am-8am Dark 8am-1pm Light:1pm-4pm Darkfor 10 heads per day is recommended since it has a positive effect on body weight can be not stressful of the broilers chicken
2. Conduct the same study in other species and types of farm animals are recommended.

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